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**LENGTH OF SERVICE AS KEY FACTOR FOR THE EFFECTIVENESS AND
WORTHINESS OF RELATIONSHIP MANAGERS IN AN ORGANISATIONAL
GROWTH**

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Abstract

This research paper emphasises on the need for achievement, power and affiliation of relationship managers and their worthiness affected by their length of service. As the needs are the motives that initiate the individuals for their output and equally their effectiveness and worthiness at both within and between the organisation. Effectiveness and worthiness is a state in which one perceives his situation as fair and justified in comparison to the co-workers within and outside the organization equally. This research has been conducted on 21 relationship managers in ICICI Life Insurance Company, New Delhi. The key results of this research show that the length of service of relationship managers have significant effects on achievement, power and affiliation needs, effectiveness and worthiness which are positively promoted by length of service.

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INTRODUCTION

With the exception of the issue of male and female differences, probably no issue is more subject to myths and speculation than the impact of seniority on effectiveness and worthiness in job. Gordon and Fitzgibbons (1982) have conducted extensive review of seniority productivity relationship. Seniority as length of service itself is not a good predictor of productivity. It is also noted service length or seniority is negatively related to absenteeism (Garrison and Muchinsky, 1977). Satisfactions of employee's needs are positively related with their length of service. A. Bedeian, et. al (1992).

Effectiveness and worthiness plays key role in up keeping motivation. Relationship managers make comparison of their job input and outcomes relative to those of others. They perceive what they get from Job situations (outcome) in relation to what they put into it (input) and then they compare their outcome input ratio of relevant others. If they perceive their ratio to be equal to that of relevant others with whom we compare ourselves, a state of equity is said to exist. They perceive their situation as fair that justice prevails, But when they see the ratio unequal, there is

equity tension. This negative tension state provides the motivation to do something to correct in (Adams, J.S. 1965).

Relationship managers of an organization might compare themselves to friends, neighbours, co-workers, colleagues in other organization or past jobs they themselves have had. Which referent a relationship manager chooses will be influenced by the information the employee holds about referents as well as by the attractiveness of the referent. This leads to focussing of the relationship manager's salary amount, level of education and length of tenure (Goodman 1989). Relationship manager with short tenure of length of service in their current organization tends to have little information about others inside the organization, so they rely on their own personal experience. On the other hand, relationship managers with long length of service rely more heavily on co-workers for comparison. It is also important to note that individuals are concerned not only with the absolute amount of rewards they receive from their efforts, but also with the relationships of this amount to what others receive. The base of one's inputs, such as efforts, experience, education and competence and comparison

of his outcomes are such as salary level raise, recognition and other factors. When relationship managers perceive an imbalance in their outcome/input ratio relative to other relationship managers, as a result of this tension arises.

Some people who have a compelling drive to succeed are striving for personal achievement rather than the rewards for success. They have a desire to do something better or more effectively than it has been done before. This drive is the achievement need. High achiever differentiates themselves from others by their desire to do something better (McClland, 1961). These people seek situations where they receive rapid feedback on their performance so that they can tell easily whether they are improving or not and where they can set moderately challenging goals. They dislike gambling with high odds because they get no achievement satisfaction from happenstance success. Similarly, they dislike low odds because there is no challenge to their skills.

The need to power is to make others behave in a way that they would not have behaved otherwise. It is a desire to have impact, to influence others. They ever like to be placing themselves into competitive and

status oriented situations. Power need oriented relationship managers tend to be more concerned with prestige and gaining influence over others than with effective performance. Relationship managers with high affiliation motive, on the other hand, strives more than the competitive ones and have high desire relationships involving a high degree of mutual understanding.

1. AIM OF THE STUDY

The present study focuses on the effectiveness and worthiness related to power, achievement and affiliation in relationship managers by the length of services. Increase in service length of relationship managers may develop the desire for respect from other relationship managers. Seniors expect not only power but also higher achievement in the organization. Affiliation to the organization is also related with service length. The newly appointed relationship managers do not have so strong attachment as the old relationship managers do.

2. METHOD

3.1 Sample

The present study was conducted on the relationship managers working in ICICI Life Insurance Company in New Delhi. The

selection of relationship managers for study was based on their availability and desirability with the permission of concerned authority. Elements of the study were 21 relationship managers. They were categorized into three classes with an interval of 4 yrs. of service length. In each class of 'service length experience' the number of elements were 9,7,5 respectively.

3.2 Tools

The test for the measurement of needs viz. Achievement, Power and Affiliation at five point rating scale by Rastores & D. Braustein and effectiveness & worthiness by Prof. Richard. C. Hussein University of Central Florida was used. Five questions were asked for effectiveness and worthiness at 10 point rating scale giving the weightage to the two described ends of each question. Both the tools were administered individually establishing good rapport with subjects.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The collected data was statistically analyzed using t-test and r. The results are accordingly discussed and conclusions are drawn as under. Relationship managers differ significantly on achievement need in respect to their service length. Within 4-8

years of service length they are more achievement oriented whereas the beginners under five years of job experience persist achievement need significantly less ($t = 2.75, P < 0.05$). Relationship managers, about 6 years service length, are also looser in achievement need persistence ($t = 0.94$, non-significantly).

It appears that first 4 years of service of relationship manager is a period to be familiar with setup, developing understanding with co-workers and establishing acquaintance. They try to achieve high and high in comparison to new corners and others. This period where relationship managers 4-8 years are actually used to show their full potential and skill on the job. They desire to do something better or more efficiently than beginning of their service period. After ten or twelve years of service relationship managers were found having reduction in this compelling drive to succeed. During four to eight years of service they strive for personal achievement but later eight or twelve years service they expect more for reward than their efforts ($t = 2.77, P < 0.05$).

Relationship managers during 4-8 years of service try their best to place themselves into competitive and status oriented situation

($t = 2.40$, $P < 0.05$). They tend to be more concerned with prestige and gaining influence over others. No significant difference has been found among different service length group of relationship managers on affiliation need. Even though the mean value for affiliation need is highest in 4-8 years of service length among all groups of relationship managers. They are friendlier, perform cooperative behaviour and have a desire for mutual understanding.

Effectiveness and worthiness in relationship managers is found differing significantly among groups of different service length. Above 8 years of service length experience relationship managers are highly effective and worthy ($t = 3.83$, $P < 0.05$) to outcome/input ratio with other co-status worker within or outside industrial setup in comparison to 1-4 years service length. Relationship managers 4-8 years of service length are also less effective and worthy.

Service length and effectiveness & worthiness correlation was found +0.24. It was a very slight association in between the service length and effectiveness and worthiness. The possibility of slight visibility of association between effectiveness & worthiness and service length might be due to high variability and

small size of the sample available for the study.

It might be concluded that during 4-12 years of service length relationship managers are more power and achievement oriented. They show more power and achievement orientation they show more cooperation and friendships among them. This period is full of competitions and status orientation. They try to dominate and influence over others.

Relationship managers are more concerned after 8 years of services experience in comparing themselves with outcome/input ratio. They expect more outcome than their juniors that is significantly lower in beginners and near to retirements. Relationship managers fewer than 8 years of service length feel satisfied what they get from their organization. Although the rank-difference correlation has not shown high association between effectiveness & worthiness and length of service of relationship managers.

5. CONCLUSION

This is a scientific study of human behaviour in the workplace which contributes to an organization's success by improving the performance, satisfaction, safety, health and well-being of its

employees with effectiveness and worthiness. We can conclude this research on employee behaviours and attitudes, and evolve with methodology to be used for improvement through hiring practices, training programs, feedback, and management systems etc. It is proved that worthiness and effectiveness of an employee takes support the use of teams, because teams can accomplish a much greater amount of work in a short period of time than can be accomplished by an individual contributor, and because the collective results of a group of contributors can produce higher quality deliverables. Hence five elements that experienced employee used to take care to contribute to team effectiveness are: team composition, task design, organizational resources, team reward and finally team goals.

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